

VOLTAGE REGULATION IN THE LV NETWORK WITH VARIABLE GENERATION BASED ON ONLINE MEASUREMENTS FROM SMART METERS WITH THE USE OF THE ON-LOAD TAP CHANGER

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ABSTRACT

This article presents the use of an MV/LV transformer with an On-Load Tap Changer (OLTC) to mitigate voltage issues and maximize PV generation by preventing the switch-off of the photovoltaic (PV) installation caused by inverters' overvoltage protection.

A detailed algorithm of the voltage control with OLTC is described

The article presents the criteria for selecting measurement points and the method of ensuring IT security of the Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI) system implemented in the DSO Energa Operator in the event of the need to access meters in real-time through the Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) system. A dedicated server installed in the Demilitarized Zone (DMZ) is used for direct, parallel with the AMI system, data reading from selected meters via data concentrators at stations where such a method of voltage regulation was installed.

The article presents the results of the pilot installations concerning, inter alia, the quality of voltage regulation and the possibility of greater accommodation of energy from renewable sources.

Direction for further work was indicated, consisting of the upgrade of the voltage control algorithm in HV/MV substations, enabling the mitigation of voltage problems in the LV grid.

INTRODUCTION

The increasing prevalence of PV micro-installations in Low Voltage (LV) electrical grids has resulted in voltage issues due to the inadequacy of current grid infrastructure. Specifically, PV energy production is suspended as voltage levels exceed permissible limits. To address this issue, efforts are being made to enhance the flexibility of LV grids to accommodate a greater number of PV micro-installations.

In Poland, by the end of 2022, the total installed capacity of micro PV installations reached 10 GW, representing approximately 30% of the entire system's peak load. The number of prosumers (consumers who also generate their power) is estimated to be 1.2 million, resulting in an average prosumer installation size of 8.3 kW.

The requirement that all installations above 3.68 kW be three-phase, ensure symmetrical (phase-balanced) PV generation.

The integration of weather-dependent, non-dispatchable distributed generation (DG) sources, such as PV, into LV networks has resulted in well-known issues of overvoltage and network overloads. These problems can be addressed by implementing solutions such as replacing and increasing the cross-section of low-voltage lines or shortening circuit length and building energy storage facilities. However, these approaches can be costly and have a long investment cycle.

Reactive Power Management (RPM) technique is frequently used as a potential solution to the issues of overvoltage and network overloads. This approach involves absorbing reactive power through PV inverters and controlling it remotely by a central (substation) controller or autonomously by the PV inverter. The $Q(U)$ or $\cos \varphi (P)$ characteristics used for this purpose, may be predefined for each PV inverter, or set based on the installation location in the low-voltage feeder. In Figures 1 and 2 the $Q(U)$ and $\cos \varphi (P)$ characteristics recommended by Polish DSO are depicted.

Using the same characteristics and parameters for all PV inverters may lead to an unfair limitation of active power generation depending on the installation location in the network. An example presented in [1] demonstrated that installations closest to the medium voltage substation were not subject to power curtailment, while the furthest one was limited to 1/3 of the available power.

Because of the constant changes in the grid configuration, such as new PV installations with different nominal powers, the implementation of optimal RPM technique by differentiating the droop coefficient and voltage critical point settings would require constant recalculations. In the case of central control of the characteristic's settings (figure 2), effective communication between the inverters and the central controller that allows reading the voltage at the connection point and adjusting the characteristics to the current situation is essential.

Additionally, it's worth noting that the regulatory effect of absorbing reactive power may be limited due to the relatively high resistance of the low-voltage network compared to medium and high-voltage networks.

This article presents the use of an MV/LV transformer with an OLTC to mitigate voltage issues and maximize PV generation by preventing the switch-off of the PV installation caused by inverters' overvoltage protection. The distinctive aspect of this method is the use of online voltage measurements at the Point of Connection (POC) PV systems, measured by smart meters and read by the data concentrator in the secondary substation, utilizing the existing PLC data transmission.

Figure 1. Example characteristic for Q control mode

Figure 2. Example characteristic for cos ϕ control mode

KEY POINTS OF THE ALGORITHM

The primary objective of the voltage control algorithm implemented in the new RTU in secondary substations is to ensure continuous power generation PV installations at all points in the grid, which could be disrupted if the inverters are turned off due to overvoltage protection as required by EN 50549-1 [2].

This protection is activated when the upper permissible voltage value $U_{10UL} = 1.1 U_n$ is exceeded by the voltage value U_{10} , which is calculated as the square root of the arithmetic mean of the squares of the voltages measured at least every 3 seconds for 10 minutes using a moving window approach. The phase with the highest voltage is selected for the U_{10} calculations. The inverters can be switched on again once the calculated U_{10} value falls below 2% of the permissible value ($U_{10} < 1.078 U_n$) after a minimum observation time of 60 seconds (default setting).

The control algorithm in RTU calculates the voltage value U_6 in the same way as above, but the input is the phase voltages measured by the smart meters (U_m) at the POC of the PVs within the moving window of 6 min and delivered to the controller with a delay resulted from PLC communication. If any of the calculated U_6 values for all phases in the POCs exceeds a predetermined threshold (U_{6UL}) of 1.08 times the nominal voltage ($U_6 > U_{6UL} = 1.08 U_n$), a command is issued to decrease the tap setting, resulting in a voltage drop.

If any U_6 value calculated above is lower than the set value, $U_6 < U_{6LL} = 0.92 U_n$ and the maximum calculated value U_{6max} for all measurements is lower than $U_{6max} < 1.04 U_n$, the tap is switched up (voltage increase).

The selection of smart meters from which voltages are read is based on an analysis of the location of the measurement within the LV network and considers the most distant PV installation in each feeder. In the absence of a PV installation in a particular feeder, the meter of the most distant customer is used instead. In cases of more complex network configurations, additional meters at the POC of PV systems may also be included in the readings if they have a significant impact on the voltage levels in the network. Measurements from the meter in the MV/LV substation (measurement on low-voltage busbars) are also included in the extended range, including voltages, currents, and phase angles. It is possible to update the list of meters assigned to each station that is used in the readings.

These energy meter measurements are continuously collected by communication software installed on a central dedicated server in the DMZ of the Distribution System Operator (DSO) technological network via a data concentrator located at the substation (Figure 3).

Figure 3 Information flow with cyber security scheme.

The collected data is then distributed to controllers in secondary substations via the SCADA system's technological network, separated from the AMI system's technological network, using the remote procedure call protocol encoded in JavaScript Object Notation (JSON-RPC) by sending a request to a controller.

The transmission of meter data read by the Data Concentrator Unit (DCU) to a central AMI system and any other auxiliary entities is based on a dedicated, proprietary data protocol called the Data Concentrator Simple Acquisition Protocol (DCSAP) [3]. This protocol utilizes commands consistent with the Device Language Message Specification (DLMS) protocol and data specification consistent with the COmpanion Specification for Energy Metering (COSEM) model.

The proposed control algorithm responds well to transient voltage changes (decreases) caused by PV generation reduction due to temporary cloud cover. Both direct voltage measurements in the depth of the network and the method of calculating the criterion value of voltage prevent too frequent changes of the tap changer on the one hand and on the other hand prevent PV shutdowns as a result of the activation of the 10-minute overvoltage protection.

The voltage regulation algorithm operating in this way considers the average time between switch operations resulting from the life of the OLTC estimated for 500 000 operations. The motor-driven tap changer used in the installations described below requires a time interval of at least 3 s between tap changes and the changeover time is less than 0.5 s. The number of OLTC operations during its lifetime is estimated at 500 000, which means that the average time between operations is 4 min, considering the different change frequencies during the seasons of the year.

The method of operation of the OLTC with the use of an additional energy source (battery) as the motor drive prevents the tap from remaining in an intermediate position due to the lack of the main power supply. A switching operation that has been started is always completed. As the voltage control algorithm is part of the substation control system, it is possible to adjust the position of the tap changer to the actual voltage situation before the transformer is switched on again after a long break.

CYBERSECURITY ISSUES

One of the main concerns of the proposed method of voltage control was the cybersecurity of the data exchange between the voltage regulation software installed in the substation controller belonging to the SCADA system and the meters, as the source of the voltage measurements, which are collected by the AMI system via DCU in the substation.

Cybersecurity for this data exchange was provided by deploying a dedicated server installed in the DSO Energa IT/OT network in the DMZ, with access on the one hand

to all DCUs in the AMI system and with communication possibility with all controllers in the MV/LV substations on the other. By this, total separation between SCADA and AMI systems devices at the substation was achieved. The information flow diagram is shown in Figure 3.

The second cybersecurity issue relates to unlimited access to the inverters by a third party (inverter producers) and vulnerability to a simultaneous switch-off of all inverters managed (monitored) by the producer's central software.

From a technical point of view, the most economically effective method of ensuring acceptable voltage levels is the RPM controlled by DSO using remote communication with the inverters at customers' premises. To implement this, it is required to have a legal basis for it and install in inverters an intermediary communication device connected to the communication port RS 485 in the inverter.

Currently, despite the existence of technical possibilities, such action is not implemented by Polish DSOs due to the lack of legal solutions enabling DSOs to interfere with inverters at customers' premises.

Whereas, intermediary devices, provided by inverter manufacturers, are commonly used, enabling remote monitoring of inverters by their owners. This is done through access to the controller manufacturer's servers where data on the functioning of the photovoltaic installation and data on the power grid are collected. The local home network of inverter users is used to collect data, in which the intermediary device is a foreign body installed behind a firewall, which protects the internal LAN against access from outside, i.e., public networks, and the Internet. Such a solution poses a great threat to IT security because the server monitoring the inverter can establish a VPN-encrypted connection to any programmed address - even from behind the prosumer's firewall, so this device can be used for an attack aimed at disabling the inverter or changing its settings.

The impact on the power system of the simultaneous, coordinated shutdown of inverters during their peak generation can be comparable to the shutdown of a large power unit.

USE CASE

Voltage regulation using OLTC was deployed in three installations of secondary substations implemented as part of the EUniversal project [4]. The results of the voltage control for one of them (are shown below).

LV network in this secondary substation is supplied by the 400 kVA, 15.75/0.42 kV transformer with a 9-position tap changer on the high voltage side with a range of $\pm 4 \times 2\%$ equipped with a motor drive. The voltage control range from $0.92U_n$ to $1.08U_n$, i.e. from 211.6V to 248.4V at 4.6V per tap change. According to the Polish regulation for LV network admissible voltage range is from $0.9U_n$ to $1.1U_n$.

The LV network has several feeders, the most important of which is the feeder supplying the housing estate, each of which is equipped with a PV installation with a power of 7 to 9 kW, which gives a total installed power of approx. 420 kW. In winter, the houses are heated by heat pumps. The estate is powered by a 4 x 240 mm² cable with a length of about 400 m, and the internal supply network in the estate is built with a 4 x 120 mm² cable.

The operation of the voltage regulation algorithm was presented in a situation when the voltages in the LV network measured by energy meters are lower than the permissible ones in Fig. 4 and in a situation when the voltage change trend tends to exceed its permissible limit, which is caused by the increasing value of PV generation Fig. 5.

Figure 4. Voltages and tap position by voltage increasing procedure

Figure 5 Voltages and tap position by voltage decreasing procedure

The total PV generation measured in the feeder in the substation was 180 kW which gives about 20 V of the voltage drop on the feeder.

All inverters, following the DSO requirements, were set in the constant $\cos \varphi = 1$ mode, i.e., active power generation only.

The voltage waveforms are shown in the figures:

U_m – measured voltages received from energy meters in POC of PV of other selected places,

U_6 – calculation voltage based on U_m as a 6-minute average in the moving window

U_{6LL} , U_{6UL} – threshold voltage value for the algorithm (tap change value) $U_{6LL} = 0.92U_n$; $U_{6UL} = 1.08U_n$.

The tap position is marked with a green line.

CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER WORK

The presented results indicate that power control using OLTC based on the voltage measurement in the depth of the LV network, mostly at the POC of the PV, protects against power limit violation and thus provides the possibility of uninterrupted operation of the PV installation with no power limitations and without the need to manage reactive power.

The frequency of OLTC tap-changes operation is lower than it results from the number of tap-changes over the lifetime of the OLTC.

Further research during the period of the greatest insolation and high PV generation may require resetting the algorithm's limit values.

Expected and technically justified is reactive power support in solving issues related to high-penetration PV, which needs to deploy communication solutions for effective inverters control.

In case of an insufficient range of voltage control by OLTC in the MV/LV substation voltage regulation in HV/MV substations will be investigated.

The voltage controller algorithm of the HV/MV transformer should consider the DG power generation. Instead of the day/night voltage set value (e.g. 16,2 kV/15,8 kV) the voltage setting might be dependent on the value and flow direction of the active power [5]. Lowering the HV/MV transformer voltage controller voltage setting on the MV side in case of low active power flow will allow for more deeply lowering of the voltage at the LV side

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